

CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF *CLADONIACEAE* IN PORTUGAL

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Fifty-nine taxa of the family *Cladoniaceae* (lichen-forming fungi), are reported from Portugal.

Key words: *Cladina*, *Cladonia*, *Pycnothelia*, Lichens, Flora, Portugal.

BURGAZ, A. R., AHTI, T. & CARVALHO, P., 1998 - Contribuição para o estudo das *Cladoniaceae* em Portugal. *Portugaliae Acta Biol., Sér. B, Sist.* Referência para Portugal de cinquenta e nove taxa pertencentes à família das *Cladoniaceae* (fungos liquenizados).

Palavras chaves: *Cladina*, *Cladonia*, *Pycnothelia*, Líquenes, Flora, Portugal.

Introduction

In early times the lichens of mainland Portugal were mainly studied by general botanists. They often included species of the genus *Cladonia* in their publications, e.g., VANDELLI (1788), BROTERO (1804), COLMEIRO (1867), ARNOLD (1868), HENRIQUES (1881, 1883, 1884), NEWTON (1887), CORDEIRO (1914, 1915) and COUTINHO (1916). However, the first major Portuguese lichenologist was Gonçalo Sampaio (1865-1937), who built up a good lichen herbarium which is in the Instituto de Botânica of Porto University (PO). His lichen publications were reprinted in a posthumous volume, where 36 taxa of *Cladonia* were reported (SAMPAIO 1970). Later, Carlos das Neves Tavares, a brilliant and active lichenol-

ogist collected several thousand specimens of lichens. They are preserved as a separate collection in the Botanical Garden of Lisbon (LISU). Tavares published many papers such as the Líquenes da Serra do Gerês, in which 27 taxa of *Cladonia* are reported (TAVARES 1950). Nevertheless, the Portuguese species of the *Cladoniaceae* have not been subjected to any monographic study except for a small synopsis on *Cladonia* (TAVARES 1944).

Material and methods

The study is primarily based on the material of Sampaio and Tavares herbaria and in the general lichen herbaria in Lisbon, Porto and Coimbra (COI) which were checked by Ahti and Burgaz in 1998. Also included is the material collected by the authors during several field trips in the 1990 and which is deposited in Madrid (MACB) or Helsinki (H). A short description is given only for the less known species; in the other cases bibliographic references to good descriptions are given.

All taxa were chemically tested with the colour reagents PD, K or CI, only some samples were tested by thin layer chromatography (TLC) according to standardized procedures (WHITE & JAMES 1985).

The study was based on 5,000 herbarium specimens and fresh material. The distribution maps were prepared with the material included in the text. Much more material was examined but is not cited because the collection localities were either not indicated, or were provided with insufficient detail. The records only refer to mainland Portugal. The Azores Islands and Madeira were excluded.

An account of the climate and phytogeography of the Iberian Peninsula is found in RIVAS-MARTÍNEZ (1987), whose zonal terminology is also followed here.

Species of the *Cladoniaceae* in mainland Portugal

Genus *Cladina* Nyl. section *Cladina*

Cladina arbuscula ssp. *mitis* (Sandst.) Burgaz
Nova Hedwigia 59: 400 (1994)

Description: AHTI (1961), RUOSS (1987).

Chemistry: PD-, K-.

Habitat: Has a wide altitudinal amplitude but very infrequent. It grows in granitic and heathland areas.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian but extends to the Mediterranean Region especially in areas with continental climate.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950) and AHTI (1961).

Material studied (Fig. 1): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Charcos, 1945, Tavares 233, LISU. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66969. Chãs de Tavares-Vila Mendo de Tavares, 29TPE19, 12-IX-1963, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6860, LISU. **MINHO**: Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, H, MACB 66970. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Vila Real, Arrabães, 29TNF96, 5-IV-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6612 A, LISU.

Cladina arbuscula ssp. *squarrosa* (Wallr.) Burgaz
Nova Hedwigia 55: 38 (1992)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992), RUOSS (1987).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: This is a very rare species only collected on acid substrates in the Eurosiberian Region.

General distribution: Although rare and local in Portugal, it has a wide distribution in Europe.

Discussion: It was reported by TAVARES (1950) as *C. sylvatica*.

Material studied (Fig. 2): **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66973. Serra do Açor, Benfeite, 20TNE8955, 260 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66971. Mata da Margaraça, 29TNE9152, 520 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66972. **MINHO**: Serra do Gerês, 29TNG72, Welwitsch, herb. Coutinho 51056, 51057, 51058, LISU.

Section *Tenuis* (Abbayes) Ahti

Cladina ciliata (Stirt.) Trass
Folia Cryptog. Estonica 11: 6 (1979)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992)

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-

Habitat: The yellowish usnic acid chemotype (f. *tenuis* (Flörke) Ahti) is more frequently encountered than the usnic acid-free, greyish f. *ciliata*, which is only scattered. Both have a wide altitudinal amplitude, growing in montane, meso- and supramediterranean belts.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian Region but extends to the Mediterranean Region, especially on acid substrates in oceanic localities.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950) and AHTI (1961) as *Cladonia tenuis*, and CARVALHO (1997).

Material studied, fumarprotocetraric acid chemotype (f. *ciliata*) (Fig. 3): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 780 m, 29-VIII-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2255, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra do Açor, Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66974. **MINHO**: Peso, Melgaço, 29TNG66, 12-VI-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1902, LISU. Gerês, Água de Ádega, 29TNG72, I-1920, Loureiro, COI 508.

Fumarprotocetraric and usnic acids chemotype (f. *tenuis*) (Fig. 3): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, Fóia, 29SNB3630, V-1847, Welwitsch, herb. Coutinho 50074, LISU. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Castelo de Vide, Galegos, 29SPD36, 650 m, 9-V-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2570, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Foz do Dão, 30-X-1961, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6732, LISU. Cambarinho, 29TNF60, 30-V-1972, Jalas 1771, H, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra da Lousã, Quinta da Alfocheira-Senhora da Piedade 29TNE63, 30-VIII-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 208, LISU. Prope Foz Dão, 29SNE66, 120 m, 16-XII-1961, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 157, H, LISU. Aveiro, São Jacinto, 29TNE29, 8-VIII-1963, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 186. Aveiro, Costa Nova, 29TNE29, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz 55902, H, LISU, MACB 66977, US. Serra de Buçaco, Sto. Antão, 29TNE56, 17-VI-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 201, LISU. Buçaco, Cruz Alta road, 450 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz 55883, H. **DOURO LITORAL**: Amarante, Serra do Marão, 29TNF76, 200 m, II-

1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2548, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Caldas de Rainha, 29SMD86, 25-V-1941, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. São Pedro de Muel, 29SME90, VIII-1950, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5162, LISU. **MINHO**: Cerveira, Senhora da Nogueira, 29TNG24, 16-XII-1943, Silva, herb. Tavares 1695, LISU. Serra do Gerês, Albergaria, 29TNG7928, 1-VIII-1941, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2726, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66978. **TRÁS OS MONTES** Serra do Marão, Arrabães, 29TNF96, 5-IV-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU.

Cladina mediterranea (P. A. Duvign. & Abbayes) Follmann & Hern.-Patr.
Philippia 3: 369 (1978)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992), RUOSS (1989).

Chemistry: PD-, K-. A HPLC analysis of the specimen Jalas 1718 was published by HUOVINEN & AHTI (1986).

Habitat: Sparsely distributed in thermic locations of thermo-, mesomediterranean, colline and montane belts. In earlier times very often encountered on undisturbed sandy seashore judged by many old herbarium specimens.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Mediterranean Region but extends to the Eurosiberian Region especially on acid or subneutrophilous soils.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1947), AHTI (1961) and CARVALHO (1997).

Material studied (Fig. 4): **ALGARVE**: prope Sagres, 29SNA09, II-1915, Palhinha & Mendes, herb. Coutinho 51065, LISU. Pinhal do Ludo, prox. Faro, 29SNA99, 21-V-1939, Cunha, herb. Tavares 179, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, Sta. Luzia, 29TNF90, 16-IV-1916, herb. Sampaio 1523, PO. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Entre Montosa e a Senhora da Piedade, Castelo de Vide, 29SPD36, 9-V-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2582, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Figueira da Foz, Pinhal do Urso, 29TNE12, VI-1940, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Aveiro, Gafanha da Nazaré, 29TNE29, 10-III-1942, Barros, herb. Tavares 175, LISU. Prope Miranda do Corvo, 29TNE53, 200 m, 28-X-1961, Tavares, exsic. Tavares 134, H, LISU. Serra de Buçaco, Sto. Antão, 29TNE56, 17-VI-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 184, LISU. Serra da Lousã, Senhora da Piedade 29TNE63, 3-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 180, LISU. Lagoa do Vela, 25-V-1972, Jalas 1718, H. **ESTREMADURA**: Lisboa, prope Belas, 29SMC79, 22-2-1953, 175 m, Tavares, exsic. Tavares 90, H, LISU. Lisboa, Quinta do Alazarra, 29SMC89, 19-V-1946, Durão, herb. Tavares 1693, LISU. Serra de Sintra, prox. Monserrate, 29SMC69, 19-III-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 182, LISU. Prope Cascais, 29SMC68, 23-IV-1967, Tavares, exsic. Vezda

664, H, LISU. Serra de Monsanto, Lisboa, 29SMC88, 1881, Mendoza, herb. Coutinho 51064, LISU. Arred. Setúbal, 29SNC06, 26-IX-1943, Sobrinho, herb. Tavares 181, LISU. Alfeite, 30-IV-1931, Degelius, H, UPS. **DOURO LITORAL**: Póvoa do Varzim, 29TNF2084, 20-I-1920, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2218, PO. Miramar, Senhora da Pedra, 29TNF2946, X-1887, I. Newton, herb. Sampaio s.n., LISU. Serra de Valongo, 29TNF45, X-1945, Resende, herb. Tavares 225, LISU. Luso, 6-V-1931, Degelius, H, UPS. **MINHO**: Serra d'Arga, 29TNG2430, 1899, herb. Sampaio 2700, PO.

Section *Impexae* (Abbayes) Ahti

Cladina portentosa (Dufour) Follm.

Philippia 4: 34 (1979)

Description: AHTI (1961), CLAUZADE & ROUX (1985).

Chemistry: PD-, K-. Perlatolic and usnic acids.

Habitat: It is a very common species and has a wide ecological amplitude, although it prefers acid soils.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian but extends to the Mediterranean Region being absent from south of Portugal.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950) and AHTI (1961) as *Cladonia impexa*; and JANSEN (1994). Different phenotypes earlier recognized *C. impexa* and *C. portentosa* were found growing together.

Material studied (Fig. 5): **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Entre Montosa e a Senhora da Piedade, Castelo de Vide, 29SPD36, 9-V-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2583, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Cambarinho, 29TNF60, 500 m, 30-V-1972, Suominen 1709, H. Serra do Caramulo, Vila Rei de Besteiros, 29TNF68, IX-1941, Cunha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 1000 m, 29-VIII-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2569, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Aveiro, entre Fonte Bela e Maninho, 29TNE29, 5-VIII-1967, Ormonde, COI. *Ibidem*, Costa Nova, 29TNE29, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz 55902a, H. Eirol, 29TNE39, 5-VIII-1967, Ormonde, COI, MACB 67007. Lagoa da Vela, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1489, H. Serra de Buçaco, Cruz Alta, 29TNE56, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 67005. 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz 55882, H, LISU, US. Buçaco Palace, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1801, H. Serra da Lousã, Quinta de Alfocheira, 29TNE63, 9-VII-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra do Açor, Benfeite, 29TNE85, 260 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 67003. *Ibidem*, Fraga da Pena,

29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 67004. Arcozelo das Maias, 29TNF61, 29-X-1961, herb. Tavares 6729, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL**: Santa Cruz do Bispo, 29TNF2763, XII-1880, Newton, herb. Sampaio 5462, PO. São Mamede de Infesta, 29TNF36, 10-III-1946, Lebois Fonseca, herb. Tavares 5112, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, Peninha, 29SMC69, 1-XI-1955, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 89, H, LISU. Mafra, 29SMD71, Veiga, COI. Setúbal, 29SNC06, V-1903, Cordeiro, herb. Coutinho 51110, LISU. Marinha Grande, Pinhal de Leiria, 29TNE00, 17-VIII-1994, Burgaz, H, MACB 66997. **MINHO**: Orbacém, 29TNG12, 200 m, III-1990, Jones, herb. Jones. Serra d'Arga, 29TNG2430, 1899, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2700, PO. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, X-1914, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 154, PO. Serra de Soajo, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, H, MACB 66999. Serra da Peneda, Branda da Bouça dos Homens, 29TNG55, 1000 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, H, MACB 67000. Serra Amarela, Ermida, 29TNG63, 16-VI-1995, 450 m, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66999. Ciparros a Vieira do Minho, 29TNG70, 15-VIII-1941, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra da Cabreira, Chã do Gavião, 29TNG71, 29-IX-1942, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra do Gerês, Portela do Homem, 29TNG72, 11-VIII-1941, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Entre Lindoso e a fronteira, 29TNG73, 18-VI-1958, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6402, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, H, MACB 67002. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Serra do Marão, entre Velão e Mondim de Basto, 29TNF96, 17-VI-1958, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6382A, LISU. Chaves, Seixal, 29TPG2918, 28-IX-1917, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1524, PO.

***Cladina rangiferina* (L.) Nyl.**

Not. Sällsk. Fauna Fl. Fenn. Förh. 8: 110 (1866)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K+ yellow.

Habitat: This is a rare and scarce species in Portugal. Collected on acid soils.

General distribution: Very rare in the Mediterranean Region; only collected in supramediterranean belt but extends to the Eurosiberian Region. The record from Serra de Monchique probably represents the southern outpost of its European distribution.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (Fig. 6): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, 29SNB32, 1925, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Torre, 29TPE1867, 1850 m,

VII-1995, Jones, herb. Jones. Vila Franca da Serra-Ribamondego, 29TPE29, 14-IX-1968, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **MINHO**: Serra do Gerês, Borrageira, 29TNG72, 22-IX-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1525, PO.

Cladina stygia (Fr.) Ahti
Nova Hedwigia 79: 45 (1984)

Description: AHTI & HYVÖNEN (1985)

Chemistry: PD+ red, K+ yellow.

Habitat: A very rare species growing mixed with *C. rangiferina*.

General distribution: Only collected on acid soils of the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt).

Discussion: This taxon is easily identified by its blackened base podetia bearing white of areoles. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 1): **MINHO**: Serra do Gerês, 29TNG72, Welwitsch, herb. Coutinho, 51056, 51057, LISU.

Genus *Cladonia* P. Browne

section *Cocciferae* (Delise) A. Evans

Cladonia bellidiflora (Ach.) Schaer.
Lich. Helv. Spic.: 21 (1823)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-, K-, UV++.

Habitat: A very rare, high-altitude species growing on bare soil.

General distribution: Only collected on acid soils in the Mediterranean Region (supramediterranean belt).

Discussion: The herbarium specimen is rather small.

Material studied (Fig. 7): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Fonte dos Perús-Torre, 29TPE15, 1800 m, 25-VIII-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares, LISU.

Cladonia carneola (Fr.) Fr.
Lichenogr. Eur. Reform.: 233 (1831)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-, K-.

Habitat: Collected on humus.

General distribution: Only collected on acid soils of the Mediterranean Region (supramediterranean belt). Also very rare in Spain (BURGAZ & AHTI 1994).

Discussion: Reported by JANSEN (1993).

Material studied (Fig. 8): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 68514.

Cladonia coccifera (L.) Willd.
Fl. Berol. Prodr.: 361 (1787)

Description: STENROOS (1989a, 1989b).

Chemistry: PD-, K-.

Habitat: This species is often encountered on heathlands and acid soils.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian (montane belt) but extends to the Mediterranean Region (supramediterranean belt) especially in northern half of Portugal.

Discussion: It was reported by TAVARES (1950), SAMPAIO (1970) and CARVALHO (1997, 1998), but some of the reports are based on the recent segregate *C. diversa*. No specimen of the other segregate, *C. borealis* S. Stenroos, was recorded from Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 9): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1990, Burgaz, MACB 66979. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 790 m, VIII-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1193, LISU. *Ibidem*, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66982. Caldas de Manteigas, 29TPE29, 1000 m, VIII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 162, LISU. Guarda, Vale do Forno, 29TPE59, IV-1943, Garcia, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra de Buçaco, 29TNE56, 26-V-1940, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Buçaco, 500 m, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1816, H. Serra da Lousã, Quinta de Alfocheira, 29TNE63, 7-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 160, LISU. Coimbra, 29TNE55, VI-1878, Moller, COI 182. **MINHO**: Guimarães, 29TNF68, herb. Coutinho 51216, LISU. Serra d'Arga, 29TNG2430, 1901, herb. Sampaio 181, PO. Serra da Peneda, Branda da Bouça dos Homens, 29TNG55, 1000 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.* MACB 66980. Peso, Melgaço, 29TNG6163, 12-VI-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1900, LISU. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 9-VIII-1915, Sampaio, COI 377. Serra do Gerês, Borrageira, 29TNG72, 19-VI-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2133, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66981. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Entre Vila Real e Murça, 29TPF17, 13-IV-1957, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5869, LISU. Pinhão, 29TPF26, Lopes, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU.

Cladonia digitata (L.) Hoffm.

Deutschl. Fl. 2: 124 (1796)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ yellow, K+ yellow.

Habitat: A very rare species growing on rotting wood and tree bases.

General distribution: Only collected in the Eurosiberian Region (colline and montane belts).

Discussion: It was reported by SAMPAIO (1916) and TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (Fig. 7): **MINHO**: Serra de Soajo, Adrão-Gavieira, 29TNG64, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 68519. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, XII-1902, Sampaio,

herb. Sampaio 353, PO. Serra do Gerês, Rio do Forno, 29TNG72, 13-IV-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2978, LISU.

Cladonia diversa Asperges

Cladon. Sect. Coccif. Belg. 2: 364 (1983)

Description: STENROOS (1989a, 1989b).

Chemistry: PD-, K-.

Habitat: This species is often encountered on heathlands and acid soils with *Pinus pinaster*.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt) but extends to the Mediterranean Region (supramediterranean belt) although absent from South Portugal.

Discussion: This taxon is probably more common than the records indicate. In Spain it is more frequent than *C. coccifera* s. str. (BURGAZ & AHTI 1994). New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 10): **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 450 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66985. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, Monte Pedral, 29TNF25, V-1879, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2711, PO. Porto, 1879, Newton 172, H-NYL 37995. **ESTREMADURA**: Lisboa, 29SMC89, VIII-1917, Ricardo Jorge, herb. Coutinho 51091, LISU. **MINHO**: Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 10-VIII-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 377, PO. *Ibidem*, VIII-1921, exsicc. Sampaio 300, PO. Serra de Soajo, Soajo-Adrião, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66986. Serra da Peneda, Branda da Bouça dos Homens, 29TNG55, 1000 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, H, MACB 66984. Vieira-Pinheiro, Vale de Rodrigo, 29TNG70, 27-IX-1952, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n. LISU. Serra do Gerês, Leonte, 29TNG72, 30-VII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 161, LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Vila Real, 29TPF17, V-1917, herb. Coutinho 51098, LISU.

Cladonia floerkeana (Fr.) Flörke

De Cladon.: 99 (1828)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-, K- (barbatic acid) or PD+ yellow, K+ yellow (thamnolic acid). Both chemotypes are widely distributed. The thamnolic acid chemotype has only rarely been found elsewhere (HUOVINEN *et al.* 1989).

Habitat: This species usually grows on base of *Pinus*.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt) but extends to the Mediterranean Region (meso- and supramediterranean belts).

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (barbatic acid chemotype (Fig. 11): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, VIII-1945, Tavares, herb. Tavares 231, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL**: Vila Nova de Gaia, Serra do Lilás, 29TNF35, IV-1879, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2706, PO. Arcozelo das Maias, 29TNF61, 29-X-1962, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6726, LISU. **MINHO**: Serra de Soajo, Peneda, 29TNG53, 21-VIII-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1548, PO. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 11-VIII-1915, Sampaio, COI 318 B. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2160, PO.

Thamnolic acid chemotype (Fig. 11): **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Marvão, junto ao Castelo, 29SPD36, 2-IV-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6519, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF9201, 16-IV-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 972, PO. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, VIII-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1192, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 450 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66987. **MINHO**: Braga, Bom Jesus, 29TNF5299, 9-VII-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1512, PO. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, V-1881, Couceiro, COI 187 A. *Ibidem*, XII-1920, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 363, PO. Serra do Gerês, Albergaria, 29TNG72, 10-IV-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2921, LISU.

The following specimens represent a robust and tall (1,5 cm long x 2 cm wide), totally corticate variant, which resembles the North American species *C. cristatella* Tuck., but contains only barbatic acid (no usnic acid).

Material studied: **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, 29SMC69, herb. Coutinho 51092, LISU, MACB 66983. *Ibidem*, Senhora da Peninha, XII-1849, Welwitsch, herb. Coutinho 51093, LISU. No locality, as *Cladonia cornucopioides* var. *mixta*, Welwitsch, PO.

Cladonia incrassata Flörke
De Cladon.: 21 (1828)

Description: CLAUZADE & ROUX (1985).

Chemistry: PD-, K-.

Habitat: Collected on tree bases.

General distribution: A very rare species only found in the Eurosiberian Region (colline belt).

Discussion: New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 8): **MINHO**: Britelo, 29TNG53, 16-VI-1995, 200 m, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 68523.

Cladonia macilenta Hoffm.

Deutschl. Fl. 2: 126 (1796)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992). Some specimens are exceptionally large, with podetia up to 4.5 cm x 2 mm.

Chemistry: PD+ orange yellow, K+ yellow (thamnolic acid) or PD-, K- (barbatic acid). The thamnolic acid chemotype is the dominant one in Portugal.

Habitat: On acidic soil in woodlands, on tree bases, and on rotten wood.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian Region (colline and montane belts) but extends to the Mediterranean Region (meso and supramediterranean belts).

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950) and CARVALHO (1997, 1998). SAMPAIO (1970) reported *C. bacillaris*.

Material studied, thamnolic acid present (Fig. 12): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66988. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66991. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 900 m, IX-1952, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4893, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Águeda-Mealhada, 29SNE48, 30-X-1961, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6717. Coimbra, 29TNE55, III-1881, Henriques, COI. Serra do Buçaco, 29TNE56, 10-I-1916,

Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 856, PO. Serra da Lousã, a sul da Quinta de Alfocheira, 29TNE63, 9-VIII-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra de Valongo, 29TNF45, IX-1945, Resende, herb. Tavares 226, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, 29TNF25, IV-1879, Newton, COI. *Ibidem*, 1879, Newton 71, H-NYL 38090. *Ibidem*, 1880, Newton 391, H-NYL 38104. Vila Nova de Gaia, Oliveira do Douro, V-1879, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2707, PO. **ESTREMADURA**: Cabo da Roca, 29SMC59, V-1843, Welwitsch, herb. Coutinho 51081, LISU. Serra de Sintra, 29SMC69, 11-IV-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 178, LISU. East of Veiga, 29SMD71, COI 4. **MINHO**: Guimarães, 29TNF68, herb. Coutinho 51216, LISU. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 10-VIII-1915, Sampaio, COI 381. Serra de Soajo, Soajo-Adirão, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66993. Serra da Peneda, 29TNG55, 1000 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66989.

without thamnolic acid (*C. bacillaris*) (Fig. 12): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF9201, 18-IV-1916, Sampaio, COI 982. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, 29TNF25, 20-XI-1880, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2710, PO. **MINHO**: Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, 29-VIII-1919, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2183, PO.

Cladonia pleurota (Flörke) Schaerer
Enum. Crit. Lich. Eur.: 186 (1850)

Description: STENROOS (1989a, 1989b).

Chemistry: PD-, K-.

Habitat: It grows on rotting wood.

General distribution: A very rare species collected in the supramediterranean and montane belts of the Mediterranean and Eurosiberian Regions.

Discussion: It was reported by STENROOS (1989a) from Portugal (Buçaco) in a world distribution map of the species, but the material (H) is now referred to *C. coccifera*. Reported by COUTINHO (1916).

Material studied (Fig. 13): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 68527. **MINHO**: Serra Amarela, Ermida, 450 m, 29TNG63, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 68526.

Cladonia polydactyla (Flörke) Spreng.
Syst. Veg. 4 (1): 274 (1827)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ orange, K+ yellow.

Habitat: Usually grows on rotting wood.

General distribution: A rare and scarce species in Portugal but was found in both Mediterranean and Eurosiberian Region.

Material studied (Fig. 13): **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66995. Serra do Açor, Mata da Margarça, 29TNE9152, 520 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 67008. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, 29SMC69, herb. Coutinho 51083, 51154, LISU. **MINHO**: Serra d'Arga, 29TNG2430, V-1901, herb. Sampaio 180, PO. Serra de Soajo, Adrão-Gavieira, 29TNG64, 750 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 68528. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, 29-IX-1919, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2182, PO. Portela do Homem, Serra do Gerês, 29TNG72, herb. Coutinho 51094, LISU.

Section *Unciales*

Cladonia uncialis (L.) F. H. Wigg. ssp. *biuncialis* (Hoffm.) M. Choisy

Bull. Mens. Soc. Linn. Lyon 20: 9 (1951)

Syn. *Cladonia uncialis* var. *gracillima* Samp., Lich. Portugal n° 291 (1923), nom. nud.

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-, K-, UV+.

Habitat: It grows on acid and bare soils in heathlands and pine woodlands.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian (colline and montane belts) but rarely extends to the Mediterranean Region (supramediterranean belt).

Discussion: *C. uncialis* was reported by TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (Fig. 14): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 67011. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE19, 790 m, VII-

1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1194, LISU. *Ibidem*, VIII-1915, Tavares, H, LISU. Serra da Estrela, Loriga, 900 m, 17-VII-1993, v. d. Boom 14326, H. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, 29TNF25, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2709, PO. Amarante, 29TNF76, 200 m, II-1948, Teixeira, herb. Tavares 2547, LISU. **MINHO**: Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, III-1923, Sampaio, exsicc. Sampaio 291, PO. Serra d'Arga, 29TNG2430, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 153, PO. Serra Amarela, Ermida, 29TNG63, 500 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, H, MACB 67010. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, XII-1907, Sampaio, COI. Serra da Cabreira, Chã do Gavião, 29TNG71, 29-IX-1942, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra do Gerês, Leonte, 29TNG72, 1100 m, 19-VI-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2114, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 67009. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Mirandela, 29TPF59, 14-X-1941, Lopes, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU.

Cladonia uncialis (L.) F. H. Wigg.
Prim. Fl. Holsat.: 90 (1780)
ssp. *uncialis*

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-, K-, UV- or UV+.

Habitat: This is a rare species in Portugal growing in heathlands and on acid soils.

General distribution: Very rare in the Mediterranean Region, only being collected in supramediterranean belt, but extends to the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt).

Discussion: A number of specimens show a polytomic rather than dichotomic branching pattern and are therefore tentatively referred to ssp. *uncialis* (PURVIS *et al.* 1992). The chemical and morphological variation of *C. uncialis* in Europe is in need of further studies.

Material studied (Fig 15): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE19, VIII-1945, Tavares, herb. Tavares 235, LISU. **MINHO**: Serra Amarela, Ermida, 29TNG63, 450 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 67012. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 67013. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Arrabais, 29TNF96, 5-IV-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6612, LISU.

Cladonia zopfii Vainio

Meddeland. Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn. 45: 4, 306 (1920)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-.

Habitat: It grows on heathlands with granitic rocks.

General distribution: Very rare in the Mediterranean Region, only being collected in the supramediterranean belt but extends to the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt).

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (Fig. 15): **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, Peninha, 29SMC69, 21-III-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1698, LISU. **MINHO**: Serra da Peneda, Branda da Bouça dos Homens, 29TNG55, 1000 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 67014. Serra do Gerês, Leonte, 29TNG72, 1-VIII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 203, LISU.

Section *Cladonia*

Cladonia cervicornis (Ach.) Flotow

Jahresber. Schles. Ges. Vaterl. Cult. 27: 105 (1849)

ssp. *cervicornis*

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992). Some specimens are very large, with rounded primary squamules, to 1.5 cm in diam., largely lacinate, podetia to 4 mm long, continuously corticate.

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: It grows in a variety of habitats but most commonly grows on acidic substrates.

General distribution: It is one of the commonest *Cladonia* species in Portugal. In the Mediterranean Region it has a wide altitudinal amplitude, growing from thermo- through meso- to supramediterranean belts, also reaching the Eurosiberian Region, where it is less frequent.

Discussion: The reports on *Cladonia verticillata* (*C. cervicornis* ssp. *verticillata*) by TAVARES (1950) and SAMPAIO (1970) also refer to ssp. *cervicornis*, because all of the Portuguese specimens checked were reidentified to ssp. *cervicornis*.

Material studied (Fig. 16): **ALGARVE**: Faro, 29SNA99, I-1916, herb. Coutinho 51195, LISU. Sagres, 29SNA09, II-1915, Palhinha & Mendes, herb. Coutinho 51192, LISU. Serra de Monchique, 29SNB32, II-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1407, LISU. Fóia, 29SNB33, herb. Coutinho 51201, LISU. Sítio das Águas, 29SNB8332, 350 m, VII-1996, Jones, herb. Jones 1389, LISU. Barranco do Velho, 29SNB9623, 500 m, XI-1997, Jones, herb. Jones 1446, LISU. Ribeira da Foupana, 29SPB33, 21-XII-1961, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 159, LISU. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Montemor-o-Novo-Évora, 29SNC77, 19-V-1957, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5966, LISU. Aldeia de Lede, 29SPB1165, 175 m, III-1995, Jones, herb. Jones 1354. Marvão, 29SPD36, 1-IV-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6503, LISU. **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Ferreira, 29SNC71, 20-III-1940, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66838. Seia, Castelo, 29TPE07, 17-VII-1942, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 800 m, 16-VIII-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2179, LISU. Caldas de Manteigas, 29TPE29, 1000 m, 29-VIII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 205, LISU. Barca d'Alva, 29TPF7344, 13-X-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1540, PO. **BEIRA BAIXA**: Vila Velha de Rodão-Castelo Branco, 29TPD19, 3-IV-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6580. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Coimbra, 29TNE55, VIII-1892, Araújo e Castro, herb. Coutinho, 51240, LISU. Coimbra estuary, 25-V-1972, Suominen, H. Buçaco, 29TNE56, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1811, H. Porto da Raiva, 16-XII-1961, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 159, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL**: Serra de Valongo, 29TNF45, X-1945, Resende, herb. Tavares 224, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Cascais, 29SMC68, IX-1915, herb. Coutinho 51194, LISU. Colares, Praia das Maças, 29SMC69, 14-VI-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 204. Sintra, Castelo dos Mouros, 29SMC79, 500 m, 16-III-1997, Burgaz, MACB 66956. Monsanto, Lisboa, 29SMC88, herb. Coutinho 51193, LISU. Setúbal, 29SNC06, 26-IX-1943, Sobrinho, herb. Tavares 1697. Marinha Grande, Pinhal de Leiria, 29TNE00, 17-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66839. **MINHO**: Guimarães, 29TNF68, 1847, Welwitsch, COL. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 14-VIII-1915, Sampaio, COI 440. Soajo, 29TNG63, 250 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66842. Vieira, Lagoa dos Cubos, 29TNG70, 2-X-1942, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra do Gerês, Lamas do Homem, 29TNG72, 11-IV-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2943, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66841. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Chaves, 29TPG21, 15-IV-1957, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5948, LISU. Rebordelo, 29TPG52, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, H, MACB 66840. Macedo-Mogadouro, 29TPG70, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6376.

Cladonia cervicornis (Ach.) Flotow ssp. *pulvinata* (Sandst.) Ahti

Ann. Bot. Fenn. 20: 5 (1983)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ deep yellow, K-. Psoromic and consporomic acids.

Habitat: This is a rare and scarce subspecies in Portugal, growing on acid soils.

General distribution: It was only collected in montane belt of the Eurosiberian Region. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 16): **MINHO**: Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66843.

Cladonia chlorophaea (Flörke ex Sommerf.) Spreng.

Syst. Veg. 4 (1): 273 (1827)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: Among mosses on acidic soils and in deciduous forests, probably much overlooked.

General distribution: Collected in both the Mediterranean (supramediterranean belt) and Eurosiberian (montane belt) Region.

Discussion: It was reported by TAVARES (1950) and SAMPAIO (1970).

Material studied (Fig. 17): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66920. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66916. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 800 m, 29-VIII-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2264, 2265, LISU. Guarda, Souto do Bispo, 29TPE59, 800 m, 29-V-1972, Suominen 1741, H. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, Cruz Alta, 29TNE56, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66918. Coimbra, 29TNE55, III-1881, Henriques, COI. Serra do Açor, Fraga de Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66919. **MINHO**: Entre Ambos os Rios, 29TNG53, 250 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66915. Serra do Gerês, Caldas, 29TNG72, 28-III-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2372, LISU.

Cladonia coniocraea (Flörke) Spreng.
Syst. Veg. 4(1): 272 (1827)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: A rare species growing on rotting wood in deciduous forests.

General distribution: Probably more common than the collections indicate. Collected both in the Eurosiberian (montane belt) and the Mediterranean Region (mesomediterranean belt).

Discussion: Reported by CARVALHO (1997, 1998).

Material studied (Fig. 18): **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Grândola, 29SNC32, 100 m, IV-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1491, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, Cruz Alta, 29TNE56, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66922. Serra do Açor, Mata da Margaraça, 29TNE95, 520 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66921. **MINHO**: Serra do Gerês, Preguiça, 29TNG72, 640 m, 24-III-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2405, LISU.

Cladonia cryptochlorophaea Asah.
J. Jap. Bot. 16: 711 (1940)

Description: HOLIEN & TØNSBERG (1985).

Chemistry: PD+ orange, K+ red. Cryptochlorophaeic and fumarprotocetraric acids (TLC).

Habitat: Collected on rotting wood in heathlands.

General distribution: A very rare species, only found in the mesomediterranean belt. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 25): **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 450 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 68518.

Cladonia cyathomorpha Stirt. ex Walt. Watson
J. Bot. 73: 156 (1935)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: On mossy granitic rocks, tree bases and crevices.

General distribution: This is not a common species but collected in the mesomediterranean and montane belts of both climatic regions.

Discussion: The status and delimitation of this species is in need of further studies. Reported by JANSEN (1993).

Material studied (Fig. 19): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, Monchique, 29SNB32, 800 m, 22-VII-1995, Burgaz, MACB 66945. **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: São Teotónio, 29SNB2652, IV-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1492, LISU. Grândola, 29SNC3823, 200 m, IV-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1496, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66943. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Coimbra, 29TNE55, V-1879, Moller, COI. Buçaco, 29TNE56, 450 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66944. Serra do Açor, Benfeito, 29TNE85, 260 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66941. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, Botanical Garden, 29TNF25, 2-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66952. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, Azóia, 29SMC69, 7-I-1961, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6693, LISU. **MINHO**: Serra da Peneda, Branda da Bouça dos Homens, 29TNG55, 17-VI-1995, 1000 m, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66942. Serra de Soajo, Soajo-Adirão, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66941.

Cladonia dimorpha S. Hammer
Mycotaxon 37: 339 (1990)

Description: HAMMER & AHTI (1990).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: Grows on bare soils and acidic soils in woodlands.

General distribution: In the Mediterranean Region it has a wide altitudinal amplitude, growing from thermo- and meso- to supramediterranean belts, and also reaching the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt) but is less frequent there (BURGAZ & AHTI 1998).

Discussion: Probably more frequent but overlooked because of difficulties in the identification of specimens without mature podetia. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 20): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 15-IV-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1545. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 800 m, VIII-1945, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1031, LISU. **BEIRA BAIXA**: Castelo-Branco, 29TPE31, 1903, Pacheco, COI. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Coimbra, 29TNE55, V-1879, Moller, COI. Buçaco, 29TNE56, IV-1891, Loureiro, COI. *Ibidem*, 500 m, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1846, H. Serra do Açor, Mata da Margaraça, 29TNE95, 520 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66946. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, 29TNF2857, Newton, herb. Sampaio 1545, PO. **ESTREMADURA**: Cascais, 29SMC68, 1881, herb. Coutinho COI. **MINHO**: Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, VIII-1921, Sampaio, exsicc. Sampaio 295. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, XII-1902, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 48, PO.

Cladonia fimbriata (L.) Fr.

Lichenogr. Eur. Reform.: 222 (1831)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K- or + yellowish.

Habitat: Uncommon in Portugal, growing among mosses and rotting wood on acidic soils of deciduous forests.

General distribution: Although collected in both climatic regions, is more rare in the Mediterranean Region (supramediterranean belt) than in the Eurosiberian one (montane belt).

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950), SAMPAIO (1970) and CARVALHO (1997, 1998).

Material studied (Fig. 21): **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Grândola, 29SNC32, 100 m, IV-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1491, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66947. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira,

29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66948. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra do Açor, Mata da Margarça, 29TNE95, 520 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66953. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, Botanical Garden, 29TNF25, 2-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66951. **ESTREMADURA**: Lisboa, Botanical Garden, 29SMC89, 28-III-1998, Ahti, H, MACB 66950. **MINHO**: Serra do Gerês, Preguisa, 29TNG72, 640 m, 24-III-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2405, LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Régua-Lamego, 29TPF05, VI-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Bragança, 29TPG8741, VI-1915, Palhinha e Mendes, herb. Coutinho 51215, LISU.

Cladonia gracilis (L.) Willd.

Fl. Berol. Prodr.: 363 (1787)

ssp. *gracilis*

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K+ brownish.

Habitat: Uncommon in Portugal, growing in heathlands and deciduous forests on granitic soils.

General distribution: Collected in both the Eurosiberian (montane belt) and the Mediterranean (supramediterranean belt) Region.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (Fig. 22): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra do Caramulo, 29TNE68, 28-IX-1942, Tavares, herb. Tavares 169. Viseu, Sta. Luzia, 29TNF90, 16-IV-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 975. Estrela, S^a da Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 20-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66846. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 30-VIII-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4650, LISU. Caldas de Manteigas, 29TPE29, 1000 m, 31-VIII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 171. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra do Açor, Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66844. Serra da Lousã, 29TNE63, 3-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 170, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, 29SMC69, IX-1948, herb. Coutinho 51228, LISU. **MINHO**: Serra Amarela, Ermida, 29TNG63, 500 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66845. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, III-1923, Sampaio, exsicc. Sampaio 294, LISU. Serra do Gerês, Rio do Forno, 29TNG72, 10-IV-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2946, LISU.

Cladonia grayi G. Merr. ex Sandst.

Cladon. Exsicc. n° 1847 (1929)

Description: HOLIEN & TØNSBERG (1985).

Chemistry: PD-, K-, UV+ bluish white.

Habitat: Very rare species, among mosses on acid soils.

General distribution: Collected in both the Eurosiberian (montane belt) and the Mediterranean (mesomediterranean belt) Regions but some specimens are from the 19th century. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 23): **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 450 M, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 68521. **ESTREMADURA**: Cascais, 29SMC68, 1881, Coutinho, COI. **MINHO**: Serra do Gerês, 29TNG72, IX-1884, Newton, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 6/85, PO.

Cladonia humilis (With.) J. R. Laundon

Lichenologist 16: 220 (1984)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K+ yellow, or K-. Most of the material apparently contains atranorin besides fumarprotocetraric acid.

Habitat: It grows among mosses or on bare and acid soils in woodlands.

General distribution: Infrequently encountered but in the Mediterranean Region has a wide altitudinal amplitude from thermo-, meso- to supramediterranean belts, and more rarely reaching the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt).

Discussion: Probably more frequent but overlooked. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 24): **ALGARVE**: Faro, 29SNA99, II-1915, Palhinha & Mendes, herb. Coutinho 51223, LISU. **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Quinta da Ortiga, 29SNC20, XI-1997, Jones, herb. Jones 1449, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66928. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66923. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Aveiro, Costa Nova, 29TNE29, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66927. Coimbra, 29TNE55,

XII-1878, Henriques, COI 122. Serra do Açor, Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66925. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, 29TNF25, Newton, COI. Porto, Fanzeres, 29TNF35, Newton, herb. Sampaio 99, PO. **ESTREMADURA**: Cascais, 29SMC68, 1881, Coutinho, COI. Serra de Sintra, 29SMC69, XII-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares 3529, LISU. Queluz, 29SMC79, II-1909, Santos, herb. Coutinho 51221, LISU. **MINHO**: Viana do Castelo, 29TNG11, VI-1886, Cunha, herb. Coutinho 51169, LISU. Serra de Soajo, Soajo-Adrão, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 64808. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Vila Real, 29TPF17, XI-1915, herb. Coutinho 1218, LISU. Bragança, 29TPG84, VI-1918, Palhinha & Mendes, herb. Coutinho 51215, LISU.

Cladonia merochlorophaea Asahina

J. Jap. Bot. 16: 713 (1940)

Description: HOLIEN & TØNSBERG (1985).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-. 4-0-methylcryptochlorophaeic, merochlorophaeic and submerochlorophaeic acids (TLC).

Habitat: A rare species on acid soils, usually mixed with other species.

General distribution: Very rare in the Mediterranean Region, only collected in the supramediterranean belt but extends to the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt).

Discussion: New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 26): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 16-IV-1916, Sampaio 972, COI. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Coimbra, 29TNE55, III-1881, Henriques, COI. Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66930. **MINHO**: Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, XI-1914, Sampaio 178, COI. Serra de Soajo, Soajo-Adrão, 500 m, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66929. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66931.

Cladonia novochlorophaea (Sipman) Brodo & Ahti

Can. J. Bot.: 1167 (1996)

Description: BRODO & AHTI (1996). Podetia esorediate, surface verruculose.

Chemistry: PD+ orange, K-. Homosekikaic, sekikaic and fumarprotocetraric acids (TLC).

Habitat: It was collected on humus on acidic soil.

General distribution: Only found in the oromediterranean belt. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 25): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Estrela, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 68524.

Cladonia ochrochlora Flörke

De Cladon.: 75 (1828)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: On rotting wood and tree bases.

General distribution: Widespread in the Mediterranean Region but infrequent in meso- and supramediterranean belts, also reaching the Eurosiberian Region (montane belt).

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (Fig. 27): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 16-IV-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 972, PO. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66932. Serra do Açor, Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66933. Arouca, 29TNF63, 20-III-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 179a, PO. **DOURO LITORAL**: Fanzeres, 29TNF35, VI-1879, Newton, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2712, PO. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, 29SMC69, 2-IV-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 3804, LISU. São Pedro de Muel, 29SME90, 26-VIII-1950, Luizete Rijo, herb. Tavares 5137, LISU. **MINHO**: Vieira do Minho, 29TNG70, VIII-1948, Palhinha, Tavares, herb. Tavares 3956, LISU. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, XII-1902, Sampaio, COI 62. Serra do Gerês, Leonte, 29TNG72, 1100 m, 1-VII-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2671, LISU.

Cladonia phyllophora Hoffm.

Deutshl. Fl. 2: 123 (1796)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-. Fumarprotocetraric acid.

Habitat: Scarce in Portugal, growing among mosses on granitic soils.

General distribution: Collected in both the Eurosiberian (colline and montane belts) and the Mediterranean (supramediterranean belt) Region.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (Fig. 27): **BEIRA ALTA**: Estrela, Serra da Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 20-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66957. **MINHO**: Serra Amarela, Lourido, 29TNG63, 200 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66955. Serra de Soajo, Adrão-Gavieira, 29TNG64, 750 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66954.

Cladonia pocillum (Ach.) Grognot
Pl. Crypt. Saône-et-Loire: 82 (1863)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: Widespread on basic substrates including walls and mortar, but infrequently encountered.

General distribution: Only collected in the Mediterranean Region (meso- and supramediterranean belts).

Discussion: Reported by JANSEN (1993).

Material studied (Fig. 28): **ALGARVE**: Vale da Boa Hora, 29SNB8114, 200 m, XI-1997, Jones, herb. Jones 1457, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra do Sicó, Campises, 29TNE42, 500 m, 29-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66847. Coimbra, Botanical Garden, 29TNE55, II-1892, Moller, herb. Coutinho 51173, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, 29TNF25, 11-IV-1943, Lebois Fonseca, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Sintra, 29SMC79, 9-III-1952, Lourenço & Henriques, herb. Tavares 4792, LISU. Arred. Lisboa, 29SMC89, 4-

II-1950, Tavares, herb. Tavares 3759, LISU. Serra de Montejunto, 29SMD93, 1-IV-1947, Romariz & Mendes, herb. Tavares 5094, LISU. Alcobaça, 29SMD98, III-1948, Resende, herb. Tavares 2568, LISU. Tomar, 29SND58, 25-IV-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 928.

Cladonia prolifica Ahti & Hammer
Mycotaxon 37: 342 (1990)

Description: HAMMER & AHTI (1990).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: This species is often encountered in woodlands and deciduous forests among mosses but it is not abundant.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian (montane belt) but extends to the Mediterranean Region (supramediterranean belt).

Discussion: The thalli are commonly infected by the tremellaceae fungus *Syzygospora*. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 28): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66958. Serra do Gerês, 29TNG72, COI s.n. Serra da Estrela, Malhadas do Cume, 29TPE16, 1-XI-1995, Marcos, MACB 66962. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, VIII-1945, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1033, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 450 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66959. Serra do Açor, Mata da Margarça, 29TNE95, 520 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66961. **ESTREMADURA**: Cascais, 29SMC68, 1881, Coutinho, COI. **MINHO**: Entre Ambos os Rios, 29TNG53, 250 M, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 68530. Serra da Peneda, Branda da Bouça dos Homens, 29TNG55, 1000 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66960.

Cladonia pseudopityrea Vainio
Acta Soc. Fauna Flora Fenn. 4: 452 (1887)

Primary thallus digitately lobate, with very thin, white arachnoid layer below, greenish-brown on upper side. Podetia usually up to 2 cm (rarely up to 4.5 cm) x 3 mm broad, corticate and squamulose, sometimes sorediate, slightly or not scyphose, sometimes ramified in upper part. Very often fertile, apothecia brown.

Chemistry: PD+ red, K+ yellow.

Habitat: It grows mixed with other species, mosses or bare soils.

General distribution: This is a Mediterranean element that rarely reaches the Eurosiberian Region (AHTI & PUNTILLO 1995). In Portugal is widespread from meso- to supramediterranean belts, although not very often encountered, and also reaches the montane belt.

Discussion: It is sometimes difficult to distinguish *C. pseupityrea* from *C. ramulosa*. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 29): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, Caldas, 29SNB32, 26-II-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1394. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra da Lousã, Quinta de Alfocheira, 29TNE63, 8-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 209, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, Fonte da Moura, 29TNF2857, 20-XI-1880, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2717, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Tapada de Mafra, 29SMD71, 5-IV-1958, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6105, LISU. Sintra, Castelo dos Mouros, 29SMC69, 2-I-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6460, LISU. **MINHO**: Lindoso-Fronteira, 29TNG73, 18-VI-1958, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6390, LISU.

Cladonia pulvinella S. Hammer
Mycotaxon 40: 192 (1991)

Description: HAMMER (1991)

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: It grows on calcareous, bare soil.

General distribution: A very rare species, only collected in the mesomediterranean belt.

Discussion: This species and its allies need comprehensive taxonomic studies in southern Europe (BURGAZ & AHTI 1998). New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 29): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, prox. Alvoco da Serra, 29TPEI7, IX-1953, Correia, herb. Tavares 5288, LISU.

Cladonia pyxidata (L.) Hoffm.
Deutschl. Fl. 2: 121 (1796)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: A fairly common species with wide ecological amplitude, although it prefers acidic soils and woodlands.

General distribution: Widespread in both the Mediterranean and Eurosiberian Regions and in many bioclimatic belts.

Discussion: Reported by CARVALHO (1997, 1998).

Material studied (Fig. 30): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, 29SNB32, V-1887, Moller, COI. **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66853. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66849. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, VIII-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1196, LISU. **BEIRA BAIXA**: Castelo Branco, 29TPE31, 1903, Pacheco, COI 46. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra do Sicó, Rabaçal, 29TNE42, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66851. Coimbra, 29TNE55, I-1881, Moller, herb. Coutinho 51166, LISU. Serra do Açor, Fraga de Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66854. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, Castelo dos Mouros, 29SMC69, 23-VIII-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1544, PO. Mafra, 29SMD71, E. da Viza, COI. Setúbal, 29SNC06, XI-1903, Cordeiro, herb. Coutinho 51182, LISU. **MINHO**: Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, XII-1902, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 356, PO. Serra do Gerês, Preguiça, 29TNG72, 24-III-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2430, LISU.

Cladonia ramulosa (With.) J. R. Laundon
Lichenologist 16: 225 (1984)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: On rotting wood mixed with mosses or on bare, acidic soils.

General distribution: Widespread in the Mediterranean Region from meso- to supramediterranean belt, also reaching the Eurosiberian Region (colline and montane belts).

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950) and SAMPAIO (1970) as *C. pityrea*.

Material studied (Fig. 31): **ALGARVE**: Torrinha, 29SNB61, 9-IV-1917, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1522, PO. **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66968. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 800 m, VIII-1945, Tavares, herb. Tavares 234, LISU. Caldas de Manteigas, 29TPE29, 31-VII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 239, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66963. **ESTREMADURA**: Lisboa, 29SMC89, VI-1853, Welwitsch, herb. Coutinho 51210, LISU. **MINHO**: Orbacém, 29TNG1020, 200 m, III-1990, Jones, herb. Jones. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 10-VIII-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 406, PO. Britelo, 29TNG53, 200 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66965. Soajo, 29TNG63, 250 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66966. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, 29-VIII-1919, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2183, PO. Serra do Gerês, Albergaria, 29TNG72, 2-VII-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2724, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66967.

Cladonia subcervicornis (Vain.) Kernst.

Jahresber. Staats-Oberrealschule Klagenfurt 43: 15, 32 (1900)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992). Some specimens are exceptionally large, with a primary thallus up to 1 cm broad, podetia up to 4.5 cm x 1.3 cm, sometimes up to six scyphi proliferating from center.

Chemistry: PD+ red, K+ yellow.

Habitat: One of the most frequent species with wide altitudinal amplitude growing on heathlands, humus and granitic soils.

General distribution: It is an Atlantic element distributed through Portugal, although is most frequent in the Eurosiberian Region but extends to the Mediterranean Region.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950) and CARVALHO (1997).

Material studied (Fig. 32): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, Foia, 29SNB33, 900 m, 21-II-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1406. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Castelo de Vide, 29SPD36, 9-V-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2586, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66858. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66855. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 820 m, 20-VIII-1951, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 40, H, LISU. Caldas de Manteiga, 29TPE29, 7-VIII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 196, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco forest, 29TNE56, 500 m, 25-5-1972, Suominen 1819, H. Serra da Lousã, Senhora da Piedade, 29TNE63, 19-VIII-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 194, LISU. Serra do Açor, Benfeite, 29TNE85, 260 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66856. *Ibidem*, Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66857. Arouca, 29TNF63, 20-III-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 183, PO. **DOURO LITORAL**: São Mamede de Infesta, 29TNF36, 8-XI-1945, PO. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, Castelo dos Mouros, 29SMC69, 11-IV-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **MINHO**: Braga, 29TNF59, 27-VIII-1941, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, III-1923, Sampaio, exsicc. Sampaio 297, LISU. Vieira, 29TNG70, 23-VIII-1941, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra da Cabreira, 29TNG71, VIII-1939, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **RIBATEJO**: Torres Novas da Cerveira, 29SND75, VIII-1915, Ricardo Jorge, herb. Coutinho 51198, LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Serra do Marão, 29TNF96, 15-IV-1957, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5926, LISU.

Cladonia subulata (L.) F. H. Wigg.
Prim. Fl. Holsat.: 90 (1780)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: On bare soil or granitic rocks in heaths and woodlands.

General distribution: Scarce in both the Eurosiberian and Mediterranean Regions with a wide altitudinal range.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950) and SAMPAIO (1970).

Material studied (Fig. 33): **BEIRA ALTA**: Estrela, Serra da Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 20-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66939. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 820 m, 29-VIII-1947, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 2262, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Coimbra, 29TNE55, VI-1878, Moller, COI. Buçaco, 29TNE56, 450 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66935. Serra do Açor, Benfeite, 29TNE85, 260 m, 29-III-

1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66938. Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66936. **DOURO LITORAL**: Vila Nova de Gaia, 29TNF3353, V-1879, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2714, PO. **ESTREMADURA**: Cabo da Roca, 29SMC59, IX-1848, herb. Coutinho 51226, LISU. **MINHO**: Serra do Gerês, Vacaria, 29TNG72, 460 m, 28-III-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2520, LISU. Lindoso-Fronteira, 29TNG73, 18-VI-1958, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6397, LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Régua-Lamego, 29TPF05, IV-1943, Pedrogão de Jesus, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU.

Section *Ascyphiferae* Tornab.

Cladonia furcata (Hudson) Schrad.
Spic. Fl. Germ.: 107 (1794)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: A fairly common species with wide ecological amplitude, growing on sandy seashores, heathlands and woodlands.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian Region but extends to the Mediterranean Region.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950) and CARVALHO (1997, 1998).

Material studied (Fig. 34): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, 29SNB32, V-1887, Moller, COI. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Marvão, 29SPD36, 2-IV-1995, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6540, LISU. **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Redondo-São Miguel de Machede, 29SPC27, 240 m, 31-XII-1960, Tavares, exiccc. Tavares 135, H, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Vendas de Galizes, 29TNE96, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1526, PO. Vouzela, 29TNF70, 20-VIII-1940, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66891. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Ribeira da Pragueira, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 22-X-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66889. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, VIII-1945, Tavares, herb. Tavares 167, LISU. Guarda, Lagoa Comprida, 29TPE48, 1680 m, 18-VI-1990, Jansen 9008B, H. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Aveiro, Costa Nova, 29TNE29, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66902. Serra do Sicó, Rabaçal, 29TNE42, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66898. Buçaco, Cruz Alta, 29TNE56, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66893. Serra da Lousã, Quinta de Alfocheira, 29TNE63, IX-1940, Palhinha, herb. Tavares 3575, LISU. Coja, 29TNE85, 6-X-1917, Jorge, herb. Sampaio 1521, PO. Coimbra, 29TNE55, I-1879, COI. Serra do Açor, Benfeite, 29TNE85,

360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66901. *Ibidem*, Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66899. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, 29TNF25, 1879, Newton, COI. Pampolide, 29TNF26, VI-1879, Newton, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2721, PO. São Mamede de Infesta, 29TNF36, 17-III-1946, Lebois Fonseca, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra de Valongo, 29TNF45, IX-1945, Resende, herb. Tavares 229, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Cascais, 29SMC68, 11-X-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra de Sintra, prox. Castelo dos Mouros, 29SMC69, 21-III-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1729, LISU. Lisboa, Alfeite, 29SMC89, 26-VIII-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1527. Arred. Lisboa, Paia, 29SMC89, 16-IV-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 168, LISU. Mafra, 29SMD71, Veiga, COI. Lagoa de Óbidos, 293MD86, 25-V-1941, Tavares, herb. Tavares 165, LISU. **MINHO**: Orbacém, 29TNG1020, 200 m, III-1990, Jones, herb. Jones. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 1-VII-1944, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares, COI. Serra de Soajo, Soajo-Adrao, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-IV-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66892. Peso, Melgaço, 29TNG6163, VI-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1904, LISU. Vieira, Pinheiro, 29TNG70, VIII-1948, Palhinha, herb. Tavares 3949, LISU. Serra do Gerês, Vacaria, 29TNG72, 460 m, 28-III-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2511, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66897. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Pedras Salgadas, 29TPG10, IX-1884, Newton, herb. Sampaio 99, PO.

***Cladonia rangiformis* Hoffm.**

Deutschl. Fl. 2: 114 (1796)

Description: CLAUZADE & ROUX (1985), PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: All tested PD- (but PD+ red occasionally expected), K+ yellow.

Habitat: One of the most frequent species with wide ecological amplitude. It can dominate in plant communities on undisturbed sandy seashores.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Mediterranean Region but extends to the Eurosiberian Region, but is absent from higher altitudes. Reported by TAVARES (1950).

Discussion: When fertile it can produce very thick podetia. Early authors (e.g. COUTINHO 1916) recognized the robust morphs as *C. pungens*, but it is now regarded as a synonym. *C. furcata* can be very similar (often growing mixed) but is usually easily separated by the PD- reaction (*C. rangiformis* very rarely PD+).

Material studied (Fig. 35): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, Barranco de Banho, 29SNB33, 20-II-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1404, LISU. Fonte Grande, 29SNB7422,

200 m, III-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1480, LISU. Quinta do Freixo, Benafim, 29SNB7924, III-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1481, LISU. Vale da Boa Hora, 29SNB8114, 200 M, XI-1997, Jones, herb. Jones 1457, LISU. Monte Gordo, 17-IX-1979, Schindler 9103e, H. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Alpalhão, 29SPD26, 350 m, V-1989, Jones, herb. Jones 1343. Évora, 29SNC97, 31-XII-1954, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Serra do Cercal, 29SNB2583, 341 m, IV-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1498, LISU. Grândola, 29SNC32, 100 m, IV-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1491, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Seia, 29TNE17, 16-VIII-1946, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Lourosa, Oliveira do Hospital, 29TNE96, 18-IX-1959, herb. Tavares 6649, LISU. Serra do Caramulo, Vila Rei de Besteiros, 29TNF68, IX-1941, Cunha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Viseu, 29TNF90, 18-IV-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1530, PO. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 800 m, VIII-1952, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4898, LISU. **BEIRA BAIXA**: Castelo-Branco, 29TPE21, XII-1884, Cunha, herb. Coutinho 51143, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Aveiro, Gafanha da Nazaré, 29TNE29, 1942, Barros, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Aveiro, Costa Nova, 29TNE29, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz 55900, H, MACB 66911. Serra do Sicó, Campises, 29TNE42, 500 m, 29-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66906. Coimbra, Zomberia (?), 29TNE55, 3-1881, Henriques 28, H-NYL 38282. Coimbra, 29TNE55, III-1892, Moller, herb. Coutinho 51115, LISU. Buçaco, 29TNE56, VI-1883, Loureiro, COI. *Ibidem*, 500 m, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1825, H. Lagoa da Vela, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1490, H. Serra da Lousã, 29TNE63, 3-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 187, LISU. Penacova, 29TNE65, I-1915, Palhinha, herb. Coutinho 51147, LISU. Coja, 29TNE85, 6-X-1917, Jorge, herb. Sampaio 1521, LISU. Serra do Açor, Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66912. **DOURO LITORAL**: Porto, 29TNF25, 1879, Newton, COI. 1879, Newton 176, H-NYL 38286, 1880, Newton 426, H-NYL 38304, Mindelo, 29TNF27, 22-IV-1951, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4205, LISU. Póvoa do Varzim, 29TNF28, V-1920, Sampaio, exsicc. Sampaio 293, PO. Serra de Valongo, 29TNF45, X-1945, Resende, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Pinhal de Magoite, 29SMD60, 23-XII-1957, Tavares, herb. Tavares 83. Cascais, 29SMC68, Borges, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Sintra, 29SMC79, I-1909, Santos, herb. Coutinho 51140, LISU. Lisboa, Alfeite, 29SMD82, 16-VIII-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1528, LISU. Lagoa de Óbidos, 29SMD86, 26-V-1941, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. São Pedro de Muel, 29SME90, VIII-1950, Luizete Rijo, herb. Tavares 5163, LISU. Setúbal, Esteval, 29SNC06, 26-IX-1943, Sobrinho, herb. Tavares 188, LISU. Monserrate, 28-IV-1931, Degelius, H, UPS. Marinha Grande, Pinhal de Leiria, 29TNE00, 17-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66910. Alto Estoril, 29SNF45, Borges, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **MINHO**: Orbacém, 29TNG1020, 200 m, III-1990, Jones, herb. Jones. Serra de Soajo, Soajo-Adirão, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 68535. Soajo, 29TNG63, 250 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 68533. Melgaço, Peso, 29TNG66, 21-VIII-1915, Sampaio, COI. Vieira do Minho, 29TNG70, VIII-1948, Palhinha, herb. Tavares 3948, LISU. Serra do Gerês, Vacaria, 29TNG72, 28-III-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2517, LISU. **RIBATEJO**: Alcochete, 29SNC81, X-1902, herb. Coutinho 51126, LISU. Salvaterra de Magos, 29SND13, 30-II-1947, Palhinha, herb. Tavares 3676, LISU. Santarém, 29SND24, 21-III-1998, Garcia, MACB 66908. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Chaves,

Seixal, 29TPG21, 28-IX-1917, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1529, PO. Bragança, 29TPG83, X-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 981, LISU.

Cladonia subrangiformis Sandst.

Abh. Naturwiss. Vereine Bremen 25: 165 (1922)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red (rarely deep yellow), K+ yellow.

Habitat: Sparse in Portugal, growing on calcareous soils.

General distribution: Although collected in both the Eurosiberian (colline belt) and Mediterranean (mesomediterranean belt) Regions it is not very often encountered.

Discussion: New to Portugal. The references given from Portugal by BARENDREGT *et al.* (1982) of *C. furcata* having psoromic acid instead of fumarprotocetraric acid should be assigned to *C. subrangiformis*, judged from the published photograph. The same chemotype is known from Spain (BURGAZ & AHTI 1994).

Material studied (Fig. 36): **BEIRA LITORAL**: Figueira da Foz, 29TNE14, 26-IV-1965, Fernandes & Sérgio, COL. Serra do Sicó, Campises, 29TNE42, 500 m, 29-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66913. Boa Viagem, 100 m, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1464, H. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra da Arrábida, 29SMC96, V-1842, Welwitsch, herb. Coutinho 51245, LISU. Tróia, 29SNC06, IX-1903, Cordeiro, herb. Coutinho 51099, LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Bragança, 29TPG8741, 10-IX-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 677, PO.

Section *Helopodium* (Ach.) S. Stenroos

Cladonia caespiticia (Pers.) Flörke

De Cladon.: 8 (1827)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: Pd+ red, K-.

Habitat: On earth banks (especially along roads) and tree bases.

General distribution: Widespread in forested areas of the Mediterranean Region from meso- to supramediterranean belts, and also reaching the Eurosiberian Region (colline and montane belts). Probably much more frequent than the collections indicate.

Discussion: Reported by SAMPAIO (1916) and TAVARES (1946, 1950).

Material studied (Fig. 37): **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, VIII-1945, Tavares, herb. Tavares 157, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66887. Serra da Lousã, a sul da Quinta de Alfocheira, 29TNE63, 26-VIII-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 159, LISU. Serra do Açor, Mata da Margarça, 29TNE95, 520 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66885. **DOURO LITORAL**: Valongo, Reboredo, 29TNF4454, 18-VII-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 359, PO. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, prox. Castelo dos Mouros, 29SMC69, 29-XII-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 158, LISU. Arred. Lisboa, Paia, 29SMC89, 1940, Oeiras, herb. Tavares s. n. LISU. **MINHO**: Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 1-VII-1944, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares, COI s.n. Entre Ambos os Rios, 29TNG53, 250 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, H, MACB 68513. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, 1-IX-1919, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1958, PO. Serra do Gerês, Parque Tude de Sousa, 29TNG72, 24-III-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2413, LISU.

Cladonia iberica Burgaz & Ahti
Nova Hedwigia 59: 430 (1994)

Description: BURGAZ & AHTI (1994).

Chemistry: PD-, K+ yellow.

Habitat: On bare, acid soils.

General distribution: Widespread in southwest Portugal, in general in the mesomediterranean belt, rarely reaching the Eurosiberian Region (colline belt).

Discussion: Tavares had recognized this species as new, under an unpublished name. Sometimes difficult to separate from *C. subturgida* but the smaller squamules with bluish to brownish underside are characteristic of *C. iberica*. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 38): **ALGARVE**: Sagres-São Vicente, 29SNA09, 30 m, 3-II-1962, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 211 (sub *C. symphycarpa*), LISU. Serra de Monchique, Caldas, 29SNB32, 26-II-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1402, LISU. Pinhal de Marim, Olhão, 29SPA09, III-1951, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4151, LISU. Ponte da Ribeira de Tábua, 29SPB34, III-1951, Tavares, herb. Tavares 432, LISU. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Bencatel-Redondo, 29SPC38, 24-XII-1953, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5428, LISU. **BEIRA BAIXA**: Vila Velha de Rodão-Castelo Branco, 29TPD19, 3-IV-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6580, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra do Sicó, Campises, 29TNE42, 500 m, 29-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 68522. Alfocheira, 29TNE63, 17-XII-1961, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6762, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Lisboa, Mata do Alfeite, 29SMC89, 7-V-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 242, LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Bragança-Milhão, 29SPG92, 4-IV-1959, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6609, LISU.

Cladonia macrophylla (Schaer.) Stenh.
Lich. Suec. exsicc., ed. 2, n° 186 (1865)

Recently reported from Serra da Estrela (APTROOT *et al.* 1992).

Cladonia subcariosa Nyl.
Flora 59: 560 (1876)
Incl. *C. polycarpoides* Nyl. in Zwackh, Lich. exsicc. n° 626, 626 bis (1892)

Description: Primary thallus squamulose, shortly lobate, white arachnoid below, greenish upper side, to 2-5 cm long x 1.5 cm broad, bearing pycnidia. Podetia very short, to 3x5-10 mm, flattened, almost solid, with loose, longitudinal fibrose structure, smooth, upper parts areolate and verruculose to squamulose, undivided or with some branchlets. Apothecia brownish.

Chemistry: PD+ red (slow reaction), K+ red (norstictic acid).

Habitat: It grows preferably on bare, subneutrophilous or acid soils.

General distribution: In southwest Portugal, generally distributed in mesomediterranean belt, rarely reaching the Eurosiberian Region (colline belt).

Discussion: SAMPAIO (1919) published it as *C. cariosa*. *C. polycarpoides* is often recognized as a distinct species but is here regarded as a chemotype of *C. subcariosa*. New to Portugal.

Material studied (Fig. 39): **ALGARVE**: Serra de Monchique, Caldas de Monchique, 29SNB32, 20-II-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1403, LISU. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Évora, 29SNC97, 29-V-1957, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5975, LISU. **RIBATEJO**: Ferreira do Zêzere, Águas Belas, 29SND69, 17-V-1942, Barros, herb. Tavares 192, LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Bragança, 29TPG8731, 10-IX-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1510 L, PO.

Cladonia suburgida Samp.

Ann. Sci. Acad. Polytechn. Porto 13: 38 (1918)

Description: SAMPAIO (1918).

Chemistry: PD+ reddish, K+ yellow.

Habitat: On granitic soils with *Pinus pinaster*.

General distribution: This is a very rare and locally distributed species, the bigger and white underside squamules serve to distinguish it from *C. iberica*. It was discussed by BURGAZ & AHTI (1994) and reported from Spain. However, it belongs to the still problematic, chemically variable *C. subcariosa*.

Material studied (Fig. 39): **BEIRA ALTA**: Guarda, Barca d'Alva, 29TPF74, 13-XII-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1245, HOLOTYPE, PO.

Subsection *Foliosae*

Cladonia convoluta (Lam.) Anders

Strauch- & Blattflechten Nordböhlm.: 29 (1906)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K+ yellowish.

Habitat: It is fairly common species and has a wide ecological amplitude, although prefers neutrophilous and basic soils.

General distribution: It is widespread in the Mediterranean Region (thermo-, meso- to supramediterranean belts) although reaches the Eurosiberian Region, too.

Discussion: Reported by SAMPAIO (1970).

Material studied (Fig. 40): **ALGARVE**: Sagres, 29SNA09, II-1915, Palhinha & Mendes, herb. Coutinho 51248, LISU. Faro, Pinhal do Ludo, 29SNA99, Cunha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Portimão, 29SNB4108, 7-IV-1917, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1517, PO. Olhão, 29SPA09, V-1847, herb. Coutinho 51246, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra do Sicó, Rabaçal, 29TNE42, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66859. Santa Clara near Coimbra, 29TNE55, 1881, Ferreira 33, H-NYL 38776. Coimbra, 29TNE55, Araújo e Castro, IV-1892, COI. **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Setúbal, Península de Tróia, 29SNC06, 1-VI-1978, Grandvaux Barbosa 12845, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL**: Pampolide, 29TNF26, X-1887, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2724, PO. Leça da Palmeira, Matosinhos, 29TNF36, 9-XII-1945, Lebois Fonseca, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Cascais, 29SMC68, 1881, Coutinho, COI. Sintra, 29SMC69, 22-XII-1955, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5773, LISU. Lisboa, 29SMC89, 20-II-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares 3012, LISU. Odívelas, 29SMC89, 1-VIII-1948, Pinto, herb. Tavares 3649, LISU. Ericeira, 29SMD61, 50 m, 22-XII-1955, Tavares, exsicc. Tavares 91, LISU. Mafra, 29SMD71, COI. Óbidos, 29SMD86, 7-XII-1953, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5315, LISU. Alcobaça, 29SMD98, III-1948, Sobrinho, herb. Tavares 2567, LISU. Serra dos Candeiros, Olhos de Água, 29SND05, 29-XII-1953, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5499. Alto Estoril, 29SNF45, 14-IV-1943, Borges, herb. Tavares 3873. **RIBATEJO**: Alferrare de Verde, 29SND7170, XI-1985, Jones, herb. Jones 1034.

Cladonia firma (Nyl.) Nyl.
Bot. Zeitung (Berlin) 19: 352 (1861)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ red, K+ yellow.

Habitat: It is fairly common species with wide ecological amplitude, growing on sandy seashore, heathlands and woodlands.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Mediterranean Region but extends to the Eurosiberian Region.

Discussion: This species used to be called *Cladonia nylanderi* Cout. (COUTINHO 1916), which is a superfluous name for *C. firma* (AHTI 1978). *C. firma* was neotypified (AHTI 1993) with a Portuguese specimen (see below).

Material studied (Fig. 41): **ALGARVE**: Marim, Sagres, 31-III-1951, Tavares, exicc. Tavares 39, NEOTYPE, H, ISONEOTYPES, LISU, UPS. Sagres, 29SNA09, II-1915, Palhinha & Mendes, herb. Coutinho 51207, LISU. Serra de Monchique, Caldas de Monchique, 29SNB32, 20-II-1946, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1409, LISU. Portimão, 29SNB40, 19-XII-1952, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4937, LISU. Olhão, 29SPA09, III-1951, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4153, LISU. Ponte da Ribeira de Tábuia, 29SPB34, III-1951, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4131, LISU. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Bencatel-Redondo, 29SPC38, 24-XII-1953, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5409, LISU. Marvão-Galegos, 29SPD36, 9-V-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2602, LISU. Elvas, 29SPD60, 23-XII-1953, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5392, LISU. **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Ferreira, 29SNC71, 20-III-1940, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Aldeia de Lede, 29SPB1165, 175 m, III-1995, Jones, herb. Jones 1354. Ponte do Albardão, 29SPC06, 31-XII-1954, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5620, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra do Caramulo, Alcofra, 29NE68, VIII-1941, G. da Cunha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66888. **BEIRA BAIXA**: Vila Velha de Rodão-Castelo Branco, 29TPD19, 3-IV-1959, Tavares, exicc. Tavares 136, H, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra da Lousã, Quinta de Alfocheira, 29TNE63, 7-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 186, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Cascais, 29SMC68, II-1903, herb. Coutinho 51205, LISU. Rio de Mouro-Sintra, 29SMC79, 17-II-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2985, LISU. Lisboa, 29SMC89, 7-V-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 185, LISU. **MINHO**: Vieira, 29TNG70, 2-X-1942, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **RIBATEJO**: Ferreira do Zêzere, 29SND69, 1940, G. de Barros, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Seixo de Cima, 29TPF05, 8-V-1941, Lopes, herb. Tavares s. n., LISU. Vila Real, 29TPF17, 13-IV-1957, herb. Tavares 5868, LISU. Pedras Salgadas, 29TPG10, VIII-1943, herb. Tavares 1964, LISU. Bragança, 29TPG8741, IX-1915, Sampaio, COI 676.

Cladonia foliacea (Huds.) Willd.

Fl. Berol. Prodr.: 363 (1787)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992). Some Portuguese specimens have a primary thallus up to 35 mm long x 25 mm broad, podetia up to 20 mm long x 6 mm broad.

Chemistry: PD+ red, K-.

Habitat: It is fairly common species and has a wide ecological amplitude, although prefers acid soils.

General distribution: It is widespread in the Mediterranean Region (thermo-, meso- and supramediterranean belts) although reaches the Eurosiberian Region, too.

Discussion: Reported by COUTINHO (1916). The variation and delimitation of this species towards *C. convoluta* were discussed by BURGAZ *et al.* (1993).

Material studied (Fig. 42): **ALGARVE**: Sagres, 29SNA09, V-1988, Moller, COI. Pinhal do Marim, Olhão, 29SPA09, 27-III-1951, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1730, LISU. **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Ponte do Albardão, 29SPC06, 31-XII-1954, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2619, LISU. Castelo de Vide, 29SPD36, 10-V-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2629, LISU. Elvas, 29TPD50, 23-XII-1953, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5400, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Vouzela, 29TNF70, 20-VIII-1940, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66864. Seia, 29TPE07, 19-VII-1942, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Barca d'Alva, 29TPF7344, 12-X-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1535, PO. **BEIRA BAIXA**: Castelo Branco, S. Fiel, 29TPD19, 1903, Pacheco, COI. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Aveiro, Costa Nova, 29TNE29, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66863. Serra de Lousã, Alfcocheira, 29TNE63, 17-XII-1961, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6761, LISU. Lagoa da Vela, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1491, H. **DOURO LITORAL**: Miramar, Senhora da Pedra, 29TNF2946, X-1887, Newton, Sampaio 2699, PO. Porto, Fanzeres, 29TNF35, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2723, PO. Porto, 29TNF25, 1879, Newton, COI. Póvoa do Varzim, 29TNF2084, 19-I-1920, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 2224, PO. **ESTREMADURA**: Colares, 29SMC69, 14-VI-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra de Sintra, Pena, 29SMC79, 5-IV-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1731, LISU. Albarraque, 29SMC79, 150 m, 6-III-1965, Tavares, exicc. Tavares 236, H. Lisboa, 29SMC89, 18-IV-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1692, LISU. Lagoa de Óbidos, 29SMD86, 25-V-1941, Tavares, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Setúbal, Esteval, 29SNC06, 26-IX-1943, Sobrinho, herb. Tavares 1728, LISU. **MINHO**: Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, XII-1902, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 51, PO. **RIBATEJO**: Salvaterra de Magos, 29SND13, 30-II-1947, Palminha, herb. Tavares 3677, LISU. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Chaves, 29TPG22, 28-IX-1917, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1536, PO. Rebordelo, 29PG52, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66860.

Cladonia strepsilis (Ach.) Grognot
Pl. Crypt. Saône-et-Loire 85 (1863)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ yellow, K-, C+ emerald green.

Habitat: It grows in humid areas with acid soils but it is not very often encountered.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian Region (colline and montane belts) and rarely extends to the Mediterranean Region (mesomediterranean belt) especially in areas with oceanic influence.

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1954).

Material studied (Fig. 42): **BEIRA LITORAL**: Luso, Buçaco, exposed slopes, 29TNE56, 14-VI-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 216, LISU. Serra da Lousã, Senhora da Piedade, 29TNE63, 3-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 211, LISU. **MINHO**: Ponte de Lima, 29TNG2823, VIII-1915, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio, PO. Peso, Melgaço, 29TNG66, VI-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1905, LISU. Vieira, 29TNG70, 23-VII-1952, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5172, LISU.

Section *Perviae*

Cladonia crispata (Ach.) Flot.

Wendt, Thermen Warmbrunn: 93 (1839)

var. *cetrariiformis* (Delise) Vain.

Acta Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn. 4: 392 (1887)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-, K-.

Habitat: This is a fairly abundant species collected on acid substrates.

General distribution: In the Eurosiberian Region (colline and montane belts), reaching the supramediterranean belt of the Mediterranean Region.

Discussion: Often infected by the parasitic fungus *Syzygospora* (*Tremellales*).

Material studied (Fig. 43): **BEIRA ALTA**: Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66862. Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, VIII-1946,

Tavares, herb. Tavares 1195, LISU. Caldas de Manteigas, 29TPE29, 31-VIII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 238, LISU. Serra do Caramulo, Paredes do Guarda, 29TPE59, 28-IX-1942, Tavares, herb. Tavares 169, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Serra da Lousã, 29TNE63, 3-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1696, LISU. Arcozelo das Maias, 29TNF61, 20-X-1961, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6728, LISU. **MINHO**: Orbacém, 29TNG1020, 200 m, III-1990, Jones, herb. Jones. Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, X-1914, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 176, PO. Serra da Peneda, Branda da Bouça dos Homens, 29TNG55, 1000 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 68517. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, XII-1902, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 68, PO. Vale Rodrigo, Vieira-Pinheiro, 29TNG70, 27-IX-1942, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., Serra da Cabreira, Chã do Gavião, 29TNG71, 29-IX-1942, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra do Gerês, Portela do Homem, 29TNG72, herb. Coutinho 51095, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66861.

Cladonia glauca Flörke

De Cladon.: 140 (1828)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-, K-, UV++, squamatic and barbatic (traces) acids, rarely PD+ yellow, UV-, thamnolic acid. The thamnolic acid chemotype is infrequent. Thamnolic acid appears to be a new report for *C. glauca*. However, we have earlier recorded one specimen from England (DORSET, 1979, coll. unknown, BM).

Habitat: Rarely on acid soils, more frequent on tree bases.

General distribution: It is widely distributed in both the Eurosiberian (colline and montane belts) and Mediterranean Region (meso- and supramediterranean belts).

Discussion: Reported by SAMPAIO (1918) and JANSEN (1993).

Material studied (squamatic and barbatic acid chemotype, Fig. 44): **ALTO ALENTEJO**: Castelo de Vide, 29SPD36, 9-V-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2578, LISU. **BEIRA ALTA**: Serra do Caramulo, Vila Rei de Besteiros, 29TNF68, VIII-1941, Cunha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Viseu, 29TNF90, 500 m, 26-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66869. Serra da Estrela, Estrela, Malhadas do Cume, 29TPE16, 1700 m, 1-XI-1995, Marcos *et al.*, MACB 66868. *Ibidem*, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, VIII-1945, Tavares, herb. Tavares 167, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Aveiro, 29TNE29, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66872. Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 3-IV-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66871. Serra da Lousã, 29TNE63, 3-IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 207, LISU. Serra do

Açor, Benfite, 29TNE85, 260 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66874. *Ibidem*, Fraga da Pena, 29TNE95, 360 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66873. **ESTREMADURA**: Serra de Sintra, Capuchos, 29SMC79, I-1948, Mendes, herb. Tavares 5136, LISU. Tapada de Mafra, 29SMD71, 28-I-1950, Tavares, herb. Tavares, 3423, LISU. **MINHO**: Serra de Soajo, Soajo-Adrão, 29TNG53, 500 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66865. *Ibidem*, Adrão-Gavieira, 29TNG64, 750 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, MACB 66866. Peso, Melgaço, 29TNG6163, VI-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1906, LISU. Lindoso-Fronteira, 29TNG73, 18-VI-1958, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6398, LISU. Sapiãos, 29TPG11, 700 m, 12-VIII-1994, Burgaz, MACB 66867. **TRÁS OS MONTES**: Vila Real-Murça, 29TPF17, 13-IV-1957, Tavares, herb. Tavares 5866, LISU.

Thamnolic acid chemotype (Fig. 44): **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Grândola, 29SNC3823, 200 m, IV-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1496, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL**: Serra de Valongo, 29TNF45, IX-1945, Resende, herb. Tavares 226, LISU. **ESTREMADURA**: Tapada de Mafra, 29SMD71, 5-IV-1958, Tavares, herb. Tavares 6106, LISU. Sesimbra, Casal da Cotovia, 29SMC95, II-1987, Melo, MACB 66875.

Cladonia parasitica (Hoffm.) Hoffm.
Deutschl. Fl. 2: 127 (1796)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD+ yellow. Thamnolic and barbatic acids.

Habitat: On tree bases.

General distribution: It is not very often encountered, being distributed in oceanic forested areas of the Mediterranean Region (mesomediterranean belt) but also reaching the Eurosiberian Region (colline and montane belts).

Discussion: Reported by SAMPAIO (1916) and TAVARES (1950), as *C. delicata*.

Material studied (Fig. 45): **BAIXO ALENTEJO**: Grândola, 29SNC32, 100 m, IV-1998, Jones, herb. Jones 1491, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL**: Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 68525. Serra da Lousã, 29TNE63, IX-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1691, LISU. **MINHO**: Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, 10-VIII-1915, Sampaio, exsicc. Sampaio 296, PO. Póvoa de Lanhoso, 29TNG66, XII-1902, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 354, PO. Serra do Gerês, Albergaria, 29TNG72, 2-VII-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2728, LISU.

Cladonia squamosa Hoffm.

Deutschl. Fl. 2: 125 (1796)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: K-, PD-, rarely PD+ yellow. Squamatic and barbatic (traces) acids, sometimes thamnolic acid. The thamnolic acid chemotype is distributed in very oceanic areas.

Habitat: Scattered in Portugal but frequent on Serra do Gerês growing on granitic soils and in deciduous forests, also on wood.

General distribution: More often encountered in the Eurosiberian Region (colline and montane belts) than in the Mediterranean Region (meso- and supramediterranean belts).

Discussion: Reported by TAVARES (1950).

Material studied (squamatic and barbatic acids chemotype, (Fig. 46): **BEIRA ALTA:** Serra da Estrela, Senhora do Desterro, 29TPE17, 30-VII-1951, Tavares, herb. Tavares 4657, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL:** Buçaco, 29TNE56, 500 m, 25-V-1972, Suominen 1795, H. *Ibidem*, Cruz Alta, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66884. Serra da Lousã, 29TNE63, VII-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 190, LISU. Serra do Açor, Mata da Margaraça, 29TNE95, 520 m, 29-III-1998, Ahti & Burgaz, MACB 66879. **DOURO LITORAL:** Porto, 29TNF25, 1879, Newton, COI. Santa Cruz do Bispo, 29TNF26, 14-II-1880, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2704, PO. São Mamede de Infesta, 29TNF36, 10-III-1945, Lebois Fonseca, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **ESTREMADURA:** Serra de Sintra, Fonte das Damas, 29SMC79, VIII-1942, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. **MINHO:** Ponte de Lima, Sá, 29TNG2823, IX-1914, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 178, PO. Entre Ambos os Rios, 29TNG53, 250 m, 16-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.*, H, MACB 66876. Serra de Soajo, Adrão-Gavieira, 29TNG64, 750 m, 17-VI-1995, Burgaz *et al.* MACB 66880. Peso, Melgaço, 29TNG6163, 11-VI-1947, Tavares, herb. Tavares 1901, LISU. Vieira, 29TNG70, VIII-1948, Palhinha, herb. Tavares 3951. Serra da Cabreira, 29TNG71, 1939, Palhinha, herb. Tavares s.n., LISU. Serra do Gerês, Leonte, 29TNG72, 1-VII-1944, Tavares, herb. Tavares 240, LISU.

Thamnolic acid (thamnolic acid chemotype, Fig. 47): **BEIRA LITORAL:** Buçaco, 29TNE56, IV-1891, Loureiro, herb. Coutinho 51044. *Ibidem*, 28-I-1996, Burgaz & Martínez, MACB 66883. **DOURO LITORAL:** Ramal do Meio, 29TNF25, V-1879, Newton, herb. Sampaio 2705, PO. Porto, 29TNF25, 1879, Newton 179, H-NYL 39336.

MINHO: Serra do Gerês, Borrageira, 29TNG72, 1340 m, 3-VII-1948, Tavares, herb. Tavares 2731, LISU.

Pycnothelia papillaria Dufour
Ann. Gén. Sci. Phys. 8: 46 (1821)

Description: PURVIS *et al.* (1992).

Chemistry: PD-, K+ yellow.

Habitat: On acid road banks and slopes of humid areas but not frequent.

General distribution: Most frequent in the Eurosiberian (colline and montane belts) and rarely extends to Mediterranean Region (mesomediterranean belt) especially in areas with oceanic influence.

Material studied (Fig. 48): **BEIRA ALTA:** Serra da Estrela, 29TPE17, 8-1881, Henriques 224, H-NYL 37538. *Ibidem*, Torre, 29TPE15, 25-VIII-1949, Tavares, herb. Tavares 3162, LISU. **BEIRA LITORAL:** Serra da Lousã, Quinta da Alfocheira, 29TNE63, 12-VIII-1943, Tavares, herb. Tavares 882, LISU. **DOURO LITORAL:** Porto, 29TNF25, 1879, Newton COI. 1880, Newton 367, H-NYL 37552, Newton, H-NYL 37550. **MINHO:** Braga, 29TNF59, 19-VI-1920, Sampaio, Sampaio 2376, PO. Serra do Gerês, Caldas do Gerês, 29TNG72, 21-IX-1916, Sampaio, herb. Sampaio 1724, PO.

Discussion

Although there are still many lichenologically unexplored areas in Portugal, especially in the centre and east of the country an attempt of a biogeographical analysis of the Portuguese *Cladoniaceae* is attempted.

The mountains are very favorable refugia for many suboceanic species but there are many disturbed areas affected by fires or reforestation (*Pinus*, *Eucalyptus*, *Acacia*) which have damaged the lichen flora.

There is a strong influence of the wet Atlantic winds, which allow the presence of thermophilous and hygrophilous species.

The genus *Cladina* is widespread in the Portuguese Eurosiberian Region, *C. stygia* being restricted to this area. In the north of the Mediterranean Region there is still *C. arbuscula* ssp. *squarrosa* and oceanic areas of Serra da Estrela represent the southern limit to *C. arbuscula* ssp. *mitis* and *C. ciliata* f. *ciliata*.

C. ciliata f. *tenuis*, *C. mediterranea*, *C. portentosa* and *C. rangiferina* are more frequent and widespread in the Mediterranean Region although their ecological requirements are different. *C. mediterranea* is more thermophilous while the others are more continental. *C. rangiferina* reaches Serra de Monchique in Algarve, its southernmost outpost in Europe.

The genus *Cladonia* has very few species restricted to the Eurosiberian Region, such as *C. cervicornis* ssp. *pulvinata*, *C. digitata* and *C. incrassata*.

Serra da Estrela constitutes the southernmost outpost for *C. coccifera*, *C. crispata* var. *cetrariiformis*, *C. merochlorophaea* and *C. uncialis*.

Estremadura has the southernmost occurrences of *C. caespiticia*, *C. diversa*, *C. floerkeana*, *C. gracilis*, *C. macilenta*, *C. ochrochlora*, *C. phyllophora*, *C. polydactyla*, *C. squamosa*, and *C. subulata*.

Species with distribution more or less restricted to the Mediterranean Region are *C. convoluta*, *C. dimorpha*, *C. iberica*, *C. pocillum*, *C. prolifica*, *C. pseudopityrea*, *C. ramulosa*, *C. subcariosa*, *C. subrangiformis*, and *C. subturgida*.

There are some continental species such as *C. bellidiflora*, *C. carneola*, *C. macrophylla*, and *C. novochlorophaea*, which are only found in the oromediterranean belt of Serra da Estrela.

Species with an atlantic-oceanic distribution are *C. grayi*, *C. parasitica*, *C. strepsilis*, and *C. zopfii*.

Some probably widespread species have relatively few records, e.g. *C. chlorophaea*, *C. coniocraea*, *C. cryptochlorophaea*, *C. pyxidata*, *C. pulvinella*, and have probably been much overlooked.

Frequent and widespread in Portugal are *C. cervicornis*, *C. cyathomorpha*, *C. fimbriata*, *C. firma*, *C. foliacea*, *C. furcata*, *C. glauca*, *C. humilis*, *C. rangiformis*, and *C. subcervicornis*.

The genus *Pycnothelia* is represented in the Eurosiberian and Mediterranean Region, being Serra da Estrela the southernmost outpost.

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Index

<i>Cladina arbuscula</i> ssp. <i>mitis</i>	3	<i>C. humilis</i>	24
<i>C. arbuscula</i> ssp. <i>squarrosa</i>	3	<i>C. iberica</i>	38
<i>C. ciliata</i>	4	<i>C. incrassata</i>	13
<i>C. mediterranea</i>	5	<i>C. macilenta</i>	13
<i>C. portentosa</i>	6	<i>C. macrophylla</i>	38
<i>C. rangiferina</i>	7	<i>C. merochlorophaea</i>	25
<i>C. stygia</i>	7	<i>C. novochlorophaea</i>	26
<i>Cladonia bellidiflora</i>	8	<i>C. ochrochlora</i>	26
<i>C. caespiticia</i>	37	<i>C. parasitica</i>	45
<i>C. carneola</i>	9	<i>C. phyllophora</i>	27
<i>C. cervicornis</i> ssp. <i>cervicornis</i>	17	<i>C. pleurota</i>	14
<i>C. cervicornis</i> ssp. <i>pulvinata</i>	19	<i>C. polydactyla</i>	15
<i>C. chlorophaea</i>	19	<i>C. pocillum</i>	27
<i>C. coccifera</i>	9	<i>C. prolifica</i>	28
<i>C. coniocraea</i>	20	<i>C. pseudopityrea</i>	29
<i>C. convoluta</i>	40	<i>C. pulvinella</i>	29
<i>C. crispata</i> v. <i>cetrariiformis</i>	43	<i>C. pyxidata</i>	30
<i>C. cryptochlorophaea</i>	20	<i>C. ramulosa</i>	31
<i>C. cyathomorpha</i>	21	<i>C. rangiformis</i>	34
<i>C. digitata</i>	10	<i>C. squamosa</i>	46
<i>C. dimorpha</i>	22	<i>C. strepsilis</i>	43
<i>C. diversa</i>	11	<i>C. subcariosa</i>	38
<i>C. fimbriata</i>	22	<i>C. subcervicornis</i>	31
<i>C. firma</i>	41	<i>C. subrangiformis</i>	36
<i>C. floerkeana</i>	12	<i>C. subturgida</i>	39
<i>C. foliacea</i>	42	<i>C. subulata</i>	32
<i>C. furcata</i>	33	<i>C. uncialis</i> ssp. <i>biuncialis</i>	15
<i>C. glauca</i>	44	<i>C. uncialis</i> ssp. <i>uncialis</i>	16
<i>C. gracilis</i>	23	<i>C. zopfii</i>	17
<i>C. grayi</i>	24	<i>Pycnothelia papillaria</i>	47

Figs. 1-48. Distribution of species of *Cladoniaceae* in the study areas, based on the revised herbaria and author's collections in H and MACB. 1. (□) *Cladonia arbuscula* ssp. *mitis*, (●) *C. stygia*. 2. *C. arbuscula* ssp. *squarrosa*. 3. *C. ciliata* (●) f. *ciliata*, (□) f. *tenuis*. 4. *C. mediterranea*. 5. *C. portentosa*. 6. *C. rangiferina*.

Figs. 7-12. 7. (●) *Cladonia bellidiflora*, (□) *C. digitata*. 8. (●) *C. carneola*, (□) *C. incrassata*. 9. *C. coccifera*. 10. *C. diversa*. 11. *C. floerkeana*. 12. *C. macilenta*.

Figs. 13-18. 13. (●) *Cladonia pleurota*, (□) *C. polydactyla*. 14. *C. uncialis* ssp. *biuncialis*. 15. (□) *C. uncialis* ssp. *uncialis*, (●) *C. zopfii*. 16. (□) *C. cervicornis* ssp. *cervicornis*, (●) *C. cervicornis* ssp. *pulvinata*. 17. *C. chlorophaea*. 18. *C. coniocraea*.

Figs. 19-24. 19. *Cladonia cyathomorpha*. 20. *C. dimorpha*. 21. *C. fimbriata*. 22. *C. gracilis*. 23. *C. grayi*. 24. *C. humilis*.

Figs. 25-30. 25. (●) *Cladonia cryptochlorophaea*, (□) *C. novochlorophaea*. 26. *C. merochlorophaea*. 27. (□) *C. ochrochlora*, (●) *C. phyllophora*. 28. (□) *C. pocillum*, (●) *C. prolifica*. 29. (□) *C. pseudopityrea*, (●) *C. pulvinella*. 30. *C. pyxidata*.

Figs. 31-36. 31. *Cladonia ramulosa*. 32. *C. subcervicornis*. 33. *C. subulata*. 34. *C. furcata*. 35. *C. rangiformis*. 36. *C. subrangiformis*.

Figs. 37-42. 37. *Cladonia caespiticia*. 38. *C. iberica*. 39. (□) *C. subcariosa*, (□) *C. subturgida*. 40. *C. convoluta*. 41. *C. firma*. 42. (□) *C. foliacea*, (●) *C. strepsilis*.

Figs. 43-48. 43. *Cladonia crispata* v. *cetrariiformis*. 44. *C. glauca* (□) squamatic and barbatic acids chemotype, (●) thamnolic acid chemotype. 45. *C. parasitica*. 46. *C. squamosa*, squamatic and barbatic acids chemotype. 47. *C. squamosa*, thamnolic acid chemotype. 48. *Pycnothelia papillaria*.